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AEROMECHANICS FAN RIG DARMSTADT: CHARACTERISATION OF THE STRUCTURAL BEHAVIOUR OF A MODERN TRANSONIC FAN BLISK UNDER FLUTTER CONDITIONS

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents an experimental investigation of the aeromechanical stability behaviour of a modern transonic fan blisk under flutter conditions. The measurements are conducted at the newly commissioned Fan Rig Darmstadt. Using an advanced capacitive blade tip timing system complemented by strain gauges and wall pressure transducers, the structural behaviour is characterised in detail across a wide range of speed and loading conditions.

The results reveal distinct first flap flutter being the stability limiting phenomenon across the whole speed range, exhibiting varying nodal diameters. Modal and nodal decomposition confirmed the vibration at a natural frequency as well as the formation of coherent inter-blade-phase-angles varying with the operating condition. The onset of self-excited vibrations with exponential amplitude growth rates is confirmed by the experimental estimation of time-dependent system damping becoming clearly negative while approaching the stability limit.

The detailed characterisation of the structural behaviour under flutter conditions provides a comprehensive experimental reference for the validation of numerical aeroelastic prediction tools as well as upcoming back-to-back comparisons with blade design variants. Furthermore, the work presented and the possibilities that arise with the capabilities of this new test facility can enhance the physical understanding of fan flutter mechanisms and thereby support the development of more reliable design rules for future aero engines.

Keywords: Fan, Aeromechanics, Flutter, Experimental, Blade Tip Timing

NOMENCLATURE

1F	First flap mode
ADP	Aerodynamic design point
BTTC	Blade tip timing and clearance
BLR	Boundary layer rake
EO	Engine order
FEA	Finite element analysis
FOR	Frame of reference
FRD	Fan Rig Darmstadt
LE	Leading edge
LEI	Leading edge instrumentation
M	Mode
MC	Mid-chord
MFLW	Mass flow measurement section
N95.8	95.8% of design speed
ND	Nodal diameter
NS	Near stability limit
OGV	Outlet guide vane
OP	Operating point
OPR	Once-per-revolution
RCS	Rotor casing
RE	Rotor exit

RI	Rotor inlet
SC	Settling chamber
SDOF	Single-degree of freedom
SE	Stator exit
SG	Strain gauge
SI	Stator inlet
STFT	Short-time Fourier Transform
TE	Trailing edge
TOA	Time-of-arrival
WL SLS	Working line sea-level-static
WPT	Wall pressure transducer

A	Amplitude envelope
c	Damping coefficient
f	Frequency
k	Stiffness
m	Mass
\dot{m}	Mass flow rate
n	Rotational speed
p	Pressure
q	Modal deflection
t	Time
U	Voltage
y	Circumferential deflection

α	Stagger angle
δ	Clearance
Δ	Difference
ε	Strain
ζ	Damping ratio
Π	Pressure ratio
σ	Growth rate
ϕ	Phase
ω	Angular frequency

<input type="checkbox"/> _{b2b}	Blade-to-blade
<input type="checkbox"/> _{b2OPR}	Blade-to-Once-per-revolution
<input type="checkbox"/> _{corr}	Corrected
<input type="checkbox"/> _{inst}	Instantaneous
<input type="checkbox"/> _{max}	Maximum
<input type="checkbox"/> _{med}	Median
<input type="checkbox"/> _{norm}	Normalised
<input type="checkbox"/> _{p2p}	Probe-to-probe
<input type="checkbox"/> _R	Rotor
<input type="checkbox"/> _{ref}	Reference
<input type="checkbox"/> _{rel}	Relative
<input type="checkbox"/> _s	Static
<input type="checkbox"/> _{sb}	Single-blade
<input type="checkbox"/> _{sp}	Single-probe
<input type="checkbox"/> _t	Total
<input type="checkbox"/> _{tip}	Blade tip
<input type="checkbox"/> _{tot}	Total

<input type="checkbox"/> _{ens}	Ensemble
<input type="checkbox"/> _{rot}	Rotating frame of reference
<input type="checkbox"/> _{stat}	Stationary frame of reference
<input type="checkbox"/>	Average
<input type="checkbox"/>	Amplitude

1 INTRODUCTION

The improvement of numerical prediction methods for aeromechanics and the understanding of influencing parameters play a key role in the definition of enhanced design rules for modern aero engines. However, new modeling methods entail uncertainties and therefore demand experimental validation, especially in the complex field of fluid-structure-interaction. For this purpose, new fan blade designs, and hence underlying numerical prediction tools, need to be validated through extensive rig testing with respect to their aerodynamic and aeromechanic behaviour to ensure safe and efficient operation.

This requirement has resulted in the setup of a new fan test rig, the Fan Rig Darmstadt (FRD), that enables flexible measurement campaigns for comprehensive experimental research on fan aerodynamics and first and foremost aeromechanics. In the course of this, the former Transonic Compressor Rig Darmstadt 2 (refer to [1–4]) of the Institute of Gas Turbines and Aerospace Propulsion at the Technical University of Darmstadt was redesigned to test fan configurations across different engine architectures. The project is carried out in cooperation with Rolls-Royce plc within the HEAVEN project as part of the EU Clean Aviation program in the framework of Horizon Europe (Grant Agreement No. 101102004).

The main objective of the FRD within this project is to perform extensive back-to-back measurements on varying fan blade designs for the root cause understanding of aeroelastic phenomena, initially focusing on fan blade flutter, and the systematic validation of new design parameters accompanied by the improvement of numerical prediction tools. Eventually, different aerodynamic and aeromechanic phenomena at the stability limit will be object of experimental investigation.

The fan blade design investigated within the scope of this work is representative for a modern long-range civil engine fan and serves as the baseline case for subsequent back-to-back comparisons between variations of the same engine type. Following an initial outline of the operational envelope of the investigated baseline stage, the emphasis will be placed on a detailed characterisation of the blisk rotor's structural dynamics at the aeromechanic stability limit as it approaches flutter under varying rotational speed and loading conditions. The primary measurement technique employed for this purpose is a capacitive blade tip timing system. A detailed assessment of the aerodynamic behaviour at the same operating conditions is presented in another paper on this conference.

2 METHODOLOGIES

In the following, the test facility FRD is introduced, outlining the key features and specifications of the rig, the configuration of the core test section, and the definition of the principal measurement planes. Subsequently, the extensive instrumentation available for the investigation of both structural dynamics and aerodynamics, as well as their interaction in the context of aeromechanics, is described. The emphasis is placed on the capacitive blade tip timing system, which serves as the primary diagnostic tool for characterising the rotor’s structural dynamic behaviour within this work.

2.1 Test Rig and Instrumentation

The open-loop transonic fan test facility is operated under Mach number similarity conditions. It allows mechanical shaft speeds of up to 18,900 rpm and mass flow rates of up to 29 kg/s. Consequently, rotor-relative tip Mach numbers of up to 1.4 and overall total pressure ratios of up to 1.7 can be achieved. The rig therefore reproduces representative aerodynamic and aeroelastic conditions of modern high-speed fans and compressors at scaled geometry.

The investigated stage features a rotor diameter of 0.44 m (17.3 in), resulting in geometric scaling factors between 3 and 8, depending on the corresponding full-scale engine architecture. The hub-to-tip ratio ranges between 0.25 and 0.3.

A key feature of the facility is its modular design, which enables rapid interchange of different blisk rotors and configuration-specific modules. Among these, an extensively instrumented rotor casing allows detailed aerodynamic and structural investigations. The operating envelope of each configuration can be mapped systematically, covering the entire range from part-speed to over-speed conditions and throttle variations along the speed lines from choke up to the stability limit and beyond.

Comprehensive stability mapping is enabled by a dedicated health and safety monitoring system that continuously tracks a wide range of aerodynamic and structural-dynamic parameters in real-time. In addition, the system benefits from the institute’s long-standing experience in operating similar facilities, under comparable conditions. The test rig is further equipped with an integrated emergency bleed system, which can either be activated manually or is triggered automatically by strain gauge signals exceeding predefined limits.

The general layout of the facility is illustrated in Fig. 1 (top). Ambient air is drawn in through an intake duct and guided into a settling chamber, where a series of flow-conditioning screens ensure a homogeneous inflow to the core test section through a calibrated bell-mouth nozzle to determine the mass flow rate. The core section houses the fan stage, which is followed by the outflow section with a radial diffuser. At the exit of the diffuser, a mechanical throttle equipped with the aforementioned

FIGURE 1: OVERVIEW OF THE TEST FACILITY WITH A DETAILED VIEW ON THE CORE TEST SECTION.

emergency bleed system controls the operating condition by adjusting the outflow area. Downstream of the throttle, the air is discharged to ambient through an exhaust duct. The drive train is located behind the test section and consists of a 1.8 MW AC electric motor, a planetary gearbox, and a torquemeter.

Focusing on the core test section in the centre and bottom part of Fig. 1, the investigated baseline stage comprises a titanium-alloy blisk rotor with 20 blades, an outlet guide vane (OGV) assembly with 44 aluminium vanes mounted on a traversable ring, and 14 non-turning steel struts with symmetric NACA profiles providing structural support. Furthermore, the rig is equipped with an acoustic liner upstream of the fan inlet, which is designed to attenuate potential acoustic waves at a narrow frequency band around the expected blade flutter frequency. The intention is to prevent an upstream propagation and reflection back to the fan face of acoustic waves interacting with the actual flutter phenomenon that is to be investigated.

A newly developed telemetry system, designed in cooperation with Rolls-Royce Deutschland Ltd. & Co. KG, enables the transmission of strain-gauge signals from the rotating to the stationary frame of reference. The system consists of a front module mounted at the rotor hub behind the spinner, a signal lead through the drive shaft, and a rear module featuring a rotating bell equipped with transmitter units and a stationary antenna.

The principal measurement planes are illustrated in the schematic section view at the bottom of Fig. 1. The inflow conditions are characterised by total temperature and pressure rakes located in the settling chamber (SC) and by static pressure taps in the mass flow measurement section (MFLW). In addition, a boundary-layer rake (BLR) is positioned close to the rotor inlet (RI). The rotor inlet (RI) and rotor exit (RE) planes provide access for radially traversable probes. The main concentration of instrumentation is located at the rotor casing (RCS). An additional measurement plane is defined at the stator inlet (SI) between the RE and the OGV assembly, where total pressure and temperature sensors are installed at the OGV leading edges. At the stator and stage exit (SE) plane, all parameters required to evaluate overall stage performance are acquired. This plane also provides access for additional traversable probes.

The state-of-the-art steady-state (low temporal resolution) instrumentation for performance measurements was designed in-house and includes, among other components, circumferentially traversable OGV leading edge probes, combined total pressure and temperature rakes, and a five-hole-probe rake. Multiple static wall pressure taps are distributed along the hub and shroud throughout the test section. In addition, five-hole-probe measurements provide high spatial resolution of the steady flow field in the RI, RE and SE planes. In total, the rig is equipped with about 220 pressure and 90 temperature ports sampled at a frequency of 100 Hz.

The focus of the experimental investigations, however, is on unsteady aerodynamic and aeromechanical phenomena. Consequently, the test rig, particularly the RCS, is extensively instrumented with time-resolving sensors (high temporal resolution with $f_{\text{sampling}} > 1$ kHz). For the acquisition of unsteady aerodynamic data, more than 80 flush-mounted

miniature wall pressure transducers (WPTs) are installed to measure static pressure with sampling frequencies up to 1.3 MHz. In addition, the 2D flow field can be measured via an in-house designed fast-response pressure probe, with built-in transducers of the same type, operated in a virtual multi-hole mode.

An axial array of WPTs is embedded in the rotor casing covering the entire axial rotor blade tip chord as well as a section of equal extent upstream of the rotor leading edge (see Fig. 2, blue) capturing shock and expansion regions. Furthermore, single WPTs distributed across several axial planes and circumferential positions both upstream and downstream of the rotor casing are employed to detect and track acoustic waves propagating through the test section, which may interact with the blade vibration response.

Structural vibrations are monitored using both strain gauges (SG) mounted on selected rotor blades and a non-contact blade tip timing and clearance (BTTC) system based on capacitive probes flush-mounted in the rotor casing. Thus, measurements are performed simultaneously in the rotating and stationary frames of reference (FOR).

A total of sixteen strain gauges are installed on eight rotor blades (see Fig. 2, red), serving primarily for health and safety (H&S) monitoring but also for post-processing analyses of blade vibration events. In addition, eight further strain gauges are mounted on four OGV vanes to monitor for instance potential buffeting phenomena. All strain-gauge channels are sampled at $f_{\text{sampling}} = 100$ kHz, providing high temporal resolution of the structural response.

The BTTC system represents the central measurement technique in this work regarding the post-measurement assessment of blade vibration events with the focus on characterising fan blade flutter. With respect to H&S monitoring, the BTTC system provides real-time information on the running tip clearance, rotor eccentricity and orbiting as well as a live all-blade-spectrogram on the deflection amplitudes. It consists of seven flush-mounted capacitive probes, signal amplifier modules that additionally provide the power supply for the probes, and a high-speed A/D converter card sampling with up to 10 MHz. The probes are distributed in the rotor casing at different axial and circumferential positions, as indicated schematically in Fig. 2 (green). The axial positions are determined with respect to the blade tip mode shapes that need to be resolved such that a probe is not located in a modal node but ideally at positions of maximum deflection. The circumferential positions are chosen to be able to resolve and distinguish between specific nodal diameters and engine orders of interest properly. The system setup follows the general architecture described by MTU Aero Engines AG (refer to [5, 6]). The probes as well as the data acquisition software have been acquired from MTU, whereas the post-processing analyses has recently been implemented independently in order to allow a precise time synchronisation

FIGURE 2: ROTOR INSTRUMENTATION WITH HIGH TEMPORAL RESOLUTION.

with all other measurement systems. Even though the A/D converter card samples with $f_{\text{sampling}} = 10$ MHz and an additional digital upsampling is applied, each probe essentially samples at the blade passing frequency, whereas this sampling frequency is not constant in case of a vibration event, which is an essential part of the measurement technique but entails restrictions for spectral analysis. However, the high sampling frequency of the A/D converter card and the digital upsampling are necessary to enable a proper detection of the blade-wise voltage peaks.

The underlying measurement principles of the BTTC system, namely the blade tip timing (BTT) and blade tip clearance (BTC) methods, are briefly outlined in Fig. 3. For the BTT technique, the time of arrival of each blade at each probe position is determined relative to the system internal start timestamp of the measurement, while for the BTC technique the height of the detected voltage peak ΔU is acquired. Within the post-processing, which is described in more detail in the following section 2.2, the inter-blade difference between estimated $\Delta t_{\text{estimated}}$ and measured time of arrival $\Delta t_{\text{measured}}$ as well as the difference between the once-per-revolution (OPR) signal and a single-blade time-of-arrival (TOA) Δt_{OPR} are of interest.

A key requirement for resolving fluid–structure interaction

FIGURE 3: MEASUREMENT PRINCIPLE OF THE CAPACITIVE BLADE TIP TIMING AND CLEARANCE SYSTEM.

phenomena and the associated phase relations between the aerodynamic and structural responses is the precise temporal synchronisation of all measurement systems. For this purpose, a common OPR reference signal, generated by a photoelectric trigger sensor mounted along the drive shaft, is distributed to all acquisition systems. At the beginning of each measurement, this OPR signal is attenuated for approximately 125 ms by an analogue trigger signal. During post-processing, the first attenuated OPR peak is identified in each data set, and all signals are truncated to this reference revolution to ensure consistent temporal alignment.

Initially, the BTTC system operated independently and was not synchronised with the remaining instrumentation. This was because the digitised and pre-processed BTTC data contained only timestamp information of the OPR referenced to an internal clock, without voltage-level data, which prevented detection of the attenuated OPR peak. To enable synchronisation, one of the seven BTTC probe signals, providing full voltage information, is included in the analogue trigger attenuation process. Its signal is split and recorded simultaneously in both the BTTC data acquisition system and a separate WPT data acquisition system that also captures the attenuated OPR signal.

In post-processing, the time of the attenuated blade signal is first identified in the WPT recording, and the time offset between this blade signal and the attenuated OPR is determined. The corresponding attenuated blade signal is then detected in the BTTC data, and, using the previously derived offset, the timestamp of the corresponding OPR peak within the BTTC data is derived. This OPR timestamp defines the reference revolution for synchronisation, to which all BTTC data is subsequently aligned.

2.2 Post-Processing Methods

The post-processing methods applied in this study aim to extract aerodynamic and structural data with which the steady

and quasi-steady operating conditions in the fan map as well as the unsteady aeroelastic response approaching the flutter boundary of the investigated fan rotor can be characterised. The described methods are confined to the relevant instrumentation that is employed for the analyses within this work, again focusing on BTTC methods.

2.2.1 Steady and Quasi-steady Operating Points

Steady operating points are determined from 2D flow field measurements at aerodynamically converged operating conditions. For the rotor, these are obtained using the OGV leading-edge instrumentation (LEI), and for the stage, by means of combined total pressure and temperature rakes at SE. For this purpose, the OGV is circumferentially traversed over slightly more than one vane pitch relative to the stationary instrumentation at the SE. The obtained 2D flow field is first circumferentially averaged to obtain 1D radial profiles of the flow quantities. In a second step, these profiles are radially averaged and area-weighted to derive the area-averaged, or 0D, operating point quantities. The total pressure and temperature ratios at SE are referenced to the inlet conditions in the SC. Using the same procedure, rotor-only total pressure and temperature ratios are obtained from the OGV LEI. To preserve Mach number similarity, the mass flow rate is corrected based on the inlet conditions in the SC.

Quasi-steady operating points are determined in a simplified manner during stepwise throttling manoeuvres without OGV traversing. Here, each throttle position is held only for a short period without fully stabilising the operating conditions. Consequently, only 1D radial profiles are acquired for a single relative OGV-to-instrumentation position. These profiles are radially averaged to yield quasi-steady 0D operating points, allowing faster mapping of speed lines while maintaining sufficient accuracy for subsequent analyses.

2.2.2 Rotor-relative Tip Flow Fields

The axial array of WPTs, as shown in Fig. 2 (blue, WPTs Ax.-Array), with the high temporal sampling in the stationary FOR of the rotor casing is used to resolve the rotor-relative flow field circumferentially. The accordingly allocated data is then revolution-wise ensemble-averaged yielding a rotor-relative static wall pressure field. This enables a qualitative view on the aerodynamic phenomena at the rotor tip such as compression shocks, expansion regions, tip leakage flow, local pressure disturbances and potentially emerging stall cells. Based on the corresponding standard deviation, flow regions with high unsteadiness can be highlighted while passage-wise deviations from the passage-ensemble-averaged flow field allow the assessment of blade-to-blade variations. Moreover, occurring pressure disturbances which might force, interact or even lock in with the blade structure leading to fluid-structure-interaction

induced blade vibrations, such as convective NSV or rotating stall, can be identified and tracked (see e.g. [7–10]).

2.2.3 Spectral Analysis For the spectral analysis of the time-resolved signals, a short-time Fourier transform (STFT) is performed in a sliding window. The data is sampled at a constant sampling frequency, and the segment length of the discrete Fourier transform is chosen such that a frequency resolution of $\Delta f = 5$ Hz is achieved. Adjacent segments are windowed with a suitable tapering function and overlapped to ensure continuous temporal coverage and to reduce spectral leakage. The resulting time–frequency representation allows the identification of dominant frequency components and their temporal evolution. To highlight the maximum spectral amplitudes over the measurement period, an additional peak-hold diagram is subsequently derived by determining the highest spectral amplitude occurring throughout the entire time window for each frequency bin.

This method is applied to WPT, SG and BTTC data which results in the identification of dominant frequencies in the aerodynamics (WPT) and structural dynamics (SG and BTTC) as well as in the stationary (WPT and BTTC) and rotating FOR (SG and BTTC derived). This way active modes and nodal diameters can be determined.

2.2.4 Blade Tip Timing and Clearance In the following, the different methods applied to extract geometric and vibrational information from BTTC data are briefly outlined. Four basic quantities can directly be obtained from raw data and are then further post-processed:

1. Voltage peak height of each blade signal: ΔU
2. Difference in TOA between two successive blades at a single probe: $\Delta t_{sp,b2b}$
3. Difference in TOA of a single blade between two probes: $\Delta t_{sb,p2p}$
4. Difference between TOA of a single blade at a single probe and the OPR time of the same revolution: $\Delta t_{sb,b2OPR}$

Referring to Fig. 3, these correspond to $\Delta t_{sp,b2b} = \Delta t_{measured}$ and $\Delta t_{sb,b2OPR} = \Delta t_{OPR}$.

The work from [5, 6, 11] served as a basis for the implementation and application of the following post-processing methods.

Blade Mapping and Derivation of Geometric Quantities In order to be able to allocate the single peaks and corresponding TOAs to the correct distinct blade and enable subsequent blade-individual post-processing, a reference probe and blade are determined first. For this purpose, two reference runs, one at

idle and one at full speed, are performed and the first probe that is triggered after the OPR is determined. Two reference runs at different speeds are necessary due to the high untwist of the blade. Subsequently, the first blade passing by the previously determined reference probe is defined as the reference blade. Considering the stagger angle and blade pitch, all signals of each probe at a specific axial and circumferential position can then be allocated to a distinct blade number.

The blade tip clearance is derived based on the $\ln(\Delta U)$ and a third order polynomial function. This function is obtained from a fit of the values of $\ln(\Delta U)$ and known radial distances between blade tip and probe from a previous calibration. Each probe is thereby mounted in a representative segment of the rotor casing with the correct setback and at the correct axial position relative to the rotor leading edge.

The blade stagger angle can be determined based on $\Delta t_{sb,p2p}$ between two probes in different axial positions.

Blade-individual Deflections Blade-individual deflections in the rotating FOR based on BTTC signals in the stationary FOR are derived with two different approaches depending on the transient manoeuvre that is performed during a measurement.

In case of throttling along a constant speed line, the blade deflections are derived from the difference between the measured $\Delta t_{sb,b2OPR}$ and an expected $\Delta t_{sb,b2OPR,ref}$ of a non-vibrating blade. The expected $\Delta t_{sb,b2OPR,ref}$ is dependent on the static deflection, which in turn is dependent on the centrifugal and aerodynamic load on the blade. Hence, $\Delta t_{sb,b2OPR,ref}$ is different at each speed line and throttling position. However, for transient throttling manoeuvres with relatively small changes in the outlet area, e.g. in case of a flutter run starting close to the stability limit and performing small throttling increments, $\Delta t_{sb,b2OPR,ref}$ can be approximated based on the average $\Delta t_{sb,b2OPR}$ over the first 100 revolutions of the manoeuvre. With the instantaneous rotor radius, rotational speed as well as the difference between $\Delta t_{sb,b2OPR}$ and $\Delta t_{sb,b2OPR,ref}$ of each blade at each probe, the tip deflection can be determined. As a result, seven temporally non-equidistant samples of tip deflection are obtained per revolution for each blade.

In case of a transient speed ramp (sweep), e.g. to investigate synchronous vibrations, the difference between the measured and expected $\Delta t_{sb,p2p}$ is more suitable. The previously described method would lead to a significant drift of the derived deflection over time, or rotational speed respectively, since $\Delta t_{sb,b2OPR,ref}$ changes significantly.

Spectral Analysis A spectral analysis is performed as described in section 2.2.3 on two different derived signals:

On the one hand, the derived blade-individual deflection signal of all probes is analysed, which delivers the spectral content in the rotating FOR, and resulting spectra are denoted as single-blade-spectra. Due to the unevenly distributed probes, the

blade-individual deflection signal is temporally non-equidistant. However, the STFT requires a constant sampling rate. Therefore, the signal is interpolated on an equidistant time grid applying a shape-preserving piecewise cubic interpolation prior to the spectral analysis.

On the other hand, the difference between the measured and estimated $\Delta t_{sp,b2b}$ is analysed considering all blades at one probe and is subsequently converted to a deflection amplitude with the rotor tip speed. The resulting spectra are denoted as all-blade-spectra (refer to [5, 6]) and indicate the frequency content in the stationary FOR.

Mode and Nodal Diameter Determination Based on the dominant frequencies in the single-blade-spectrogram, the structural vibration frequency of the blade is determined during a transient flutter run and compared to the predicted natural frequencies from a finite-element-analysis in order to derive the active structural modes.

Through a comparison of each identified modal frequency in the rotating FOR f_M^{rot} obtained from the single-blade-spectrogram with the most dominant frequencies in the stationary FOR f_M^{stat} , which are obtained from the all-blade-spectrogram, one can determine the active nodal diameters (NDs) through the following relation:

$$f_M^{stat} = f_M^{rot} \pm f_R \cdot ND \quad (1)$$

with + indicating a forward travelling wave and – a backward travelling wave. Or with the definition of engine order $EO = \frac{f}{f_R} = \frac{f}{n/60}$ and rewritten for ND :

$$ND = EO_M^{stat} \mp EO_M^{rot} \quad (2)$$

All derived values of ND that are an integer value considering the EO resolution of the obtained spectral data are regarded as an active ND .

Modal and Nodal Decomposition The modal deflection of each blade is extracted for each identified mode from the single-blade-spectra by applying a bandpass filter with a narrow width of ± 15 Hz around the dominant frequency of the active mode f_M^{rot} . This procedure isolates the vibration component associated with a specific structural mode, e.g. during the flutter event.

Subsequently, the contribution of each active ND to the modal deflection is derived by extracting the maximum deflection amplitude obtained from the all-blade-spectrogram within a narrow frequency band of ± 15 Hz around each associated $f_{M,ND}^{stat}$. As a result, the different ND contents in each modal deflection can be tracked over time.

Damping Estimation The total system damping ζ_{tot} of the dominant mode is derived from the time-domain single-blade tip deflection signal $y_{\text{tip}}(t)$ obtained during throttling into the flutter boundary. The estimation procedure follows a single-mode assumption and extracts the local exponential growth or decay rate of the oscillation envelope by means of analytical signal processing and robust regression.

The dominant vibration mode is approximated as a single-degree-of-freedom (SDOF) oscillator

$$m\ddot{q}(t) + c\dot{q}(t) + kq(t) = 0, \quad (3)$$

with modal frequency $\omega_0 = \sqrt{k/m}$ and damping ratio $\zeta = c/(2m\omega_0)$. For small damping, the displacement response is

$$q(t) = A_0 e^{-\zeta\omega_0 t} \sin(\omega_0 t + \phi_0), \quad (4)$$

When $\zeta < 0$, the amplitude envelope grows exponentially, indicating an unstable system condition.

The measured deflection $y_{\text{tip}}(t)$ is first zero-phase bandpass filtered around the modal frequency, obtained from the single-blade spectrogram, applying a fourth-order Butterworth filter. Subsequently, in order to obtain an instantaneous frequency f_{inst} , an analytical signal is constructed within each analysis window containing N oscillation cycles via the Hilbert transform [12, 13]. The instantaneous frequency is defined as the temporal derivative of the analytical phase $\phi(t)$. In practice, f_{inst} is estimated in a sliding window by linear regression of $\phi(t)$.

Assuming a single-mode response, the amplitude envelope follows

$$A(t) \propto e^{\sigma t}, \quad (5)$$

where σ denotes the local exponential growth (or decay) rate. Taking the logarithm gives a linear relation

$$\ln A(t) = C + \sigma t. \quad (6)$$

Within each analysis window containing N oscillation cycles, the slope σ is estimated by a robust Theil-Sen median-slope regression [14], which is less sensitive to outliers and amplitude spikes than ordinary least squares. The envelope may optionally be smoothed using a short Savitzky-Golay filter [15] to suppress high-frequency noise. Based on this, the total system damping can be derived

$$\zeta_{\text{tot}}(t) = -\frac{\sigma(t)}{2\pi f_{\text{inst}}(t)} \quad (7)$$

The pure aerodynamic contribution could be obtained by subtraction of the structural damping ratio, which could be determined for instance through vibration testing under vacuum or quasi-vacuum conditions. However, the structural contribution to the total damping is always positive and in case of a blisk rotor configuration generally assumed to be small compared to the aerodynamic contribution. Hence, an obtained negative ζ_{tot} is rather conservative and clearly denotes aerodynamic energy input to the blade and as a result an unstable system. Typical magnitudes during the onset of stall flutter events are of order 10^{-4} to 10^{-3} , depending on the mode, the corresponding frequency and operating condition.

To avoid spurious estimates in the pre-flutter region, two acceptance criteria are applied: (i) the local amplitude must exceed a signal-to-noise threshold, $A(t) > k \cdot \text{median}(A)$ with $k \in [5, 10]$, and (ii) the coefficient of determination of the log-envelope fit must satisfy $R^2 > R_{\text{min}}^2$ (typically 0.9). Values failing these criteria are rejected or replaced by a short-time average of neighbouring valid points. These steps substantially reduce apparent fluctuations before the actual onset of flutter.

The statistical properties and bias of exponential-fit or logarithmic-decrement estimators are discussed in detail in [16] and [17]. Their analyses motivate the amplitude- and R^2 -based gating adopted here.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the following, the experimental results obtained from the first measurement campaign at the FRD on a modern transonic fan blisk are presented and discussed. The discussion is divided into two main parts addressing first the aerodynamic and structural behaviour of the fan stage across its stable operating envelope, and second the detailed flutter characteristics at the stability limit.

The first part focuses on a brief characterisation of the operating envelope based on steady, quasi-steady and transient measurements. Detailed mapping from choke to near-stability conditions and from part-speed through design speed to overspeed is performed. This includes steady performance measurements along selected speed lines as well as transient stability mapping. Four steady operating points at two speed lines, part-speed and design speed, are exemplarily assessed in detail. Additionally, the transient response during run-ups at constant throttle conditions is investigated.

The second part addresses the stability limit in detail and concentrates on selected flutter onsets associated with different dominant nodal diameters. The active mode and nodal diameter are identified from the BTTC spectra and validated through comparison with WPT and SG spectrograms. Along different speed lines, various nodal diameters are found to be active or dominant. Based on this identification, the evolution of nodal diameter contents in the 1F modal deflection amplitude

approaching flutter is analysed. Subsequently, the temporal evolution of the modal and total deflection of a selected blade is shown, and instantaneous amplitudes of all blades are extracted to identify spatial wave patterns associated to dominant NDs.

Finally, based on the envelope of the bandpass-filtered deflection signal of an individual blade, the temporal evolution of the total system damping is estimated for flutter runs at different operational speeds. Regions exhibiting clear exponential growth in deflection amplitude indicate negative aerodynamic damping, confirming the presence of self-excited vibrations. Furthermore, blade-individual and global damping values are derived providing a quantitative measure of flutter strength and enable a comparative evaluation of different flutter onsets along the stability limit.

3.1 Operational Envelope

Figure 4 presents the experimentally derived fan map covering the speed range from 70% of the aerodynamic design speed ($N70$) up to $N105$. The mass flow rate $\dot{m}_{corr,norm}$ is corrected with the inlet conditions according to Mach number similarity and normalised to the aerodynamic design point (ADP), while the total pressure ratio $\Pi_{t,R,norm}$ shown refers to the rotor only. Quasi-steady mapping was performed in increments of $\Delta N = 2.5\%$, starting from the sea-level-static working line (WL SLS) and proceeding by stepwise throttling towards the stability limit. At the end of each speed line, dedicated flutter runs were conducted, initiated from an operating point (OP) close to the stability limit and performed either stepwise with small throttle increments or continuously with a constant throttle-closing rate. For this first test campaign, the emergency bleed system was activated when the measured strain reached between 25% (amber limit) and 50% (red limit) of the blade endurance limit. In addition, detailed steady performance measurements were carried out along three selected speed lines: $N70$, representing the lower part-speed boundary of interest; $N85$, where the smallest flutter margin was observed; and $N95.8$, corresponding to the shifted aerodynamic design speed line of the present configuration. The design speed differs from $N100$, as the same rotor had previously been tested with a different scaling on another facility that set the design speed.

The transient stability mapping with high speed resolution enabled the identification of the first flap mode (1F) flutter, which corresponds to blade mode 1 (M1, see Fig. 5), along the entire stability limit, exhibiting varying NDs. In the fan map, the colour of the flutter points (right before emergency bleed activation) indicates the dominant ND in deep flutter, while the marker size represents the maximum measured blade tip deflection amplitude. It should be noted that this amplitude depends on the type of flutter manoeuvre performed, with continuous runs generally producing higher amplitudes than stepwise runs. Four major ND transitions can be observed: from

FIGURE 4: EXPERIMENTAL FAN MAP AND CHARACTERISATION OF THE STABILITY LIMIT.

FIGURE 5: NUMERICALLY PREDICTED MODESHAPE OF MODE 1 (1F).

ND1 to ND2 between $N72.5$ and $N73.75$, a narrow region of ND2 reverting to ND1 between $N80$ and $N82.5$, a subsequent transition to ND3 between $N82.5$ and $N83.75$, and finally a change from ND3 to ND2 between $N87.5$ and $N90$, which remains dominant at higher-speed conditions. The largest flutter bite and hence the minimum flutter margin occurs at $N85$ with dominant ND3, while another smaller bite appears between $N72.5$ and $N77.5$ with ND2. The maximum blade deflection amplitude was measured at $N97.5$ during a continuous flutter manoeuvre. Consequently, a detailed structural analysis of the flutter characteristics is carried out in section 3.2 for three selected speed lines: $N70$ (lowest part-speed, dominant ND1), $N85$ (smallest flutter margin, ND3), and $N97.5$ (largest measured amplitudes, ND2).

The steady aerodynamic and structural behaviour within the stable operating envelope, apart from the stability limit, is

outlined in Fig. 6. Two speed lines are considered: the part-speed line at $N70$ and the aerodynamic design speed line at $N95.8$. For each, one operating point on the WL SLS and one near the stability limit (NS) are compared. Although the primary focus of this study is on structural dynamics, the aerodynamic flow conditions play a decisive role in the fluid–structure-interaction and influence the characteristics of the flutter onset. The corresponding aerodynamic analysis is presented in detail in a separate publication on this conference. However, the essential flow features at part and design speed are briefly summarised here. The WPT fields shown at the rotor tip display the static pressure ratio, ensemble-averaged over several revolutions, with two passages depicted for illustration. At $N95.8$, a pronounced compression shock can be identified clearly indicating transonic operation. At WL SLS, the shock is detached from the blade leading edge (LE), and downstream regions of expansion are visible. Interaction between the shock and the tip leakage flow is evident near the suction side between mid-chord (MC) and the trailing edge (TE). As the stage is throttled towards the NS point, loading increases, causing the shock to move upstream and further detach from the LE, while the region of shock leakage flow interaction shifts accordingly. At $N70$, no distinct shock structure can be identified in the available flow field.

The corresponding structural conditions are represented by the blade-individual relative tip clearance $\delta_{tip,rel}$, normalised with respect to the local blade height, at different axial chordwise positions. For both speed lines, the largest tip clearance occurs near the TE, while the difference between LE and TE decreases with increasing speed. Blade-to-blade variations remain within $\pm 6\%$ deviation from the median value, showing an alternating circumferential pattern. A local minimum in tip clearance is observed for blades no. 7–9 and a maximum for blades no. 17–19. Additionally, the stagger-angle variations $\Delta\alpha_{med,rel}$, expressed as relative deviations from the median, remain below 0.05%, indicating a good overall geometric uniformity of the rotor.

The evolution of relative tip clearance and blade untwist across the stable operating envelope is shown in Fig. 7. The untwist, defined as the change in stagger angle $\Delta\alpha_{idle}$ relative to idle speed, and the relative tip clearance, averaged over the three axial chordwise positions, are compared for different steady operating conditions. As expected, an overall decrease in tip clearance and an increase in untwist with increasing rotational speed, thus increased centrifugal and aerodynamic loading, are observed. Along a constant speed line, both quantities increase with rising aerodynamic loading, whereby the tip clearance exhibits an approximately linear progression, while the untwist follows a non-linear trend similar to the corresponding speed line in the fan map. The change in relative tip clearance due to increased loading lies between 0.05% and 0.09% of the local blade height, whereas the untwist variation ranges between 0.2° and 0.8°.

FIGURE 6: CHARACTERISATION OF ROTOR TIP AERODYNAMICS, BLADE INDIVIDUAL TIP CLEARANCE AND STAGGER ANGLE AT DISTINCT STEADY OPERATING CONDITIONS.

Figure 8 illustrates the transient evolution of relative tip clearance and untwist during run-up sweeps. In order to indicate synchronous resonance crossings, the upper part of the figure additionally shows the normalised blade tip deflection $y_{tip,MC,norm}$, also denoted as resonance curve, derived from a selected BTTC probe pair located at the MC axial position. Major synchronous crossings of the fundamental modes within the operating speed range are indicated. However, the corresponding response amplitudes are relatively small, implying only low synchronous forcing. The untwist is analysed for several constant throttle positions, thus constant diffuser outlet areas: a fully open throttle corresponding to the maximum outlet area (WL Choke), the WL SLS according to the design mass flow rate at ADP, and a higher throttled line (WL Higher)

FIGURE 7: DEPENDENCY OF TIP CLEARANCE AND STAGGER ANGLE ON THE STEADY OPERATING CONDITION.

situated between WL SLS and NS line. The relative tip clearance is shown for three axial chordwise positions at throttle position WL SLS.

For all throttle positions, the untwist exhibits an almost linear increase with speed up to approximately 14,000 rpm. Beyond this, the WL Choke line shows a non-linear plateau with nearly constant stagger angle up to about 16,000 rpm, followed by a renewed linear increase. At higher working lines, this non-linear region shifts to higher speeds—around 16,500 rpm for WL SLS, where an abrupt decrease in untwist is observed before a subsequent linear increase resumes. At WL Higher, the untwist remains nearly linear throughout the entire speed range. The evolution of relative tip clearance reveals a distinct variation between LE and TE at part-speed conditions. The clearance change remains linear at all axial positions but with the steepest slope at the TE, decreasing towards MC and showing

FIGURE 8: EVOLUTION OF TIP CLEARANCE AND STAGGER ANGLE DURING TRANSIENT SWEEPS CROSSING SYNCHRONOUS RESONANCES.

only minimal closure at the LE. At ADP, the LE and MC tip clearances coincide.

3.2 Stability Limit

A detailed structural analysis of selected flutter onsets at *N70*, *N85*, and *N97.5* is conducted, initially starting with the identification of the dominant structural mode and corresponding active NDs. The identification of the active mode is based on the dominant frequencies in the BTTC single-blade spectra (rotating FOR). The corresponding active NDs are determined through

FIGURE 9: COMPARISON OF SPECTROGRAMS FROM BTT, SG AND WPT APPROACHING FLUTTER AT N70 (M1 ND1).

comparison with the BTTC all-blade spectra (stationary FOR) while approaching flutter.

At $N70$, an exemplary analysis is performed that additionally includes a comparison with the aerodynamic response in the WPT spectrogram and SG measurements, as illustrated in Fig. 9. The shown colour quantity in all BTTC spectra is the blade tip deflection amplitude $\hat{y}_{\max, \text{tip}}$ scaled to the maximum at the LE according to the tip modeshape received from a FEA. The BTTC single-blade spectrogram reveals a dominant frequency at $EO_{M1}^{\text{rot}} = 1.92$, which corresponds to the M1 natural frequency at the present rotational speed. Several minor peaks observed around this dominant frequency represent higher or lower harmonics of the natural frequency as well as other frequencies. These are not considered further in the present work. A corresponding peak at $EO_{M1}^{\text{rot}} = 1.90$ is identified in the SG spectrogram, and the deviation between both frequencies lies within the EO resolution at this speed of $\Delta EO =$

FIGURE 10: BTT SPECTROGRAMS APPROACHING FLUTTER AT N85 (M1 ND3).

0.025. In the BTTC all-blade spectrogram, one clearly dominant $EO^{\text{stat}} = 2.92$ and a weaker $EO^{\text{stat}} = 4.92$ are detected. Using Eq. (2), the dominant ND is determined to be ND1 (forward travelling), while the secondary, weakly active component, corresponds to ND3. The dominant $EO_{M1, \text{ND1}}^{\text{stat}} = 2.90$ is also visible in the aerodynamic response in the WPT spectrum, appearing simultaneously with the structural frequency. No other significant aerodynamic frequencies below half the blade-passing frequency are observed. A detailed analysis of the aerodynamic frequency and phase response, however, is beyond the scope of this work and is addressed in a separate publication on this conference.

The same analysis is performed for the flutter onsets at $N85$ and $N97.5$. At $N85$, shown in Fig. 10, the dominant EO corresponding to the M1 natural frequency is identified as $EO_{M1}^{\text{rot}} = 1.69$. Based on the all-blade spectrogram, four NDs with different relative amplitudes are identified, corresponding to ND3, ND2, ND4, and ND5, in descending order of dominance.

At $N97.5$, illustrated in Fig. 11, the dominant frequency corresponding to the M1 natural frequency is found at $EO_{M1}^{\text{rot}} = 1.60$. The associated all-blade spectrogram reveals four active NDs being ND2, ND3, ND4 and ND5, again sorted by decreasing amplitude. The clear identification of these distinct modal and nodal patterns confirms that all observed flutter events are 1F with varying forward travelling NDs depending on the operating condition.

Based on the determined active NDs, the analysis now focuses on the three fundamental NDs that dominate along the stability limit, ND1, ND2, and ND3. The temporal evolution of their respective contributions to the 1F mode deflection amplitude during throttling towards flutter is shown in Fig. 12. Here, the ND content is defined as the instantaneous share of a

FIGURE 11: BTT SPECTROGRAMS APPROACHING FLUTTER AT N97.5 (M1 ND2).

specific ND, obtained from the maximum amplitude extracted from the all-blade spectrogram within a narrow EO band around the corresponding $EO_{M1,ND}^{stat}$, relative to the sum of the amplitudes of all identified M1-related NDs. This representation allows tracking of the relative strength and competition between the active spatial wave structures during the transition from stable operation to flutter.

The results indicate that the degree of interaction and competition between NDs depends on the speed line. In general, alternation between competing NDs is observed prior to flutter onset, where one ND ultimately dominates and characterises the instability. At $N70$, the two identified fundamental NDs remain well separated throughout the entire flutter run, with ND1 being dominant at all times. Only two short intervals are observed where ND2 temporarily exceeds ND1. The two curves appear nearly symmetrical around the 50% ND-content level. At $N85$, the dominant ND3 emerges only at approximately revolution -800 . Before this point, ND3 still exhibits strong activity, but three distinct regions of temporary dominance by ND2 are detected. At $N97.5$, the ND2 content, which eventually becomes dominant, initially decreases continuously until roughly revolution -1500 , reaching a similar level to ND3. Subsequently, ND2 increases sharply and becomes the clearly prevailing ND.

Based on these observed trends, two characteristic time frames are selected for each investigated speed line, as indicated in Fig. 12 with (A) and (B). The first point in time, marked as (A), is prior to flutter onset when an alternation between competing NDs occurs. The second, marked as (B), represents the condition immediately before emergency bleed activation, when the dominant ND is fully established in deep flutter. These two time frames are analysed in the following to assess the spatial

FIGURE 12: COMPARISON OF THE ALL-BLADE TEMPORAL EVOLUTION OF NODAL DIAMETER CONTENTS APPROACHING FLUTTER.

wave patterns of the identified NDs as well as their relative position to flutter onset in the raw and bandpass-filtered tip deflection signal.

The temporal evolution of the M1 deflection as well as the total deflection for a selected blade are shown in Fig. 13. In the upper right corner of each subfigure, a zoomed view of the last 5 revolutions in deep flutter is included, displaying the blade-individual signals. The plots compare the M1 bandpass-filtered BTTC deflection, the total BTTC deflection, and the inverted SG signal (the latter inverted for visualisation since a positive tip deflection corresponds to a negative strain). All BTTC deflections are normalised to the maximum absolute total deflection, while the strain signals are normalised to the maximum absolute strain of the respective SG. A good phase agreement between BTTC and SG signals can be observed, confirming the consistency and proper temporal synchronisation between the two measurement systems. Moreover, distinct phase shifts between adjacent blades, thus an inter-blade-phase-angle, can be seen. At this point, it is referred to [18] who recently published their work on a very comprehensive comparison of different blade vibration measurement techniques.

The lower right part of each subfigure shows the instantaneous blade-individual amplitudes extracted at time marker (B) at revolution -2 , representing deep flutter conditions. These amplitude distributions clearly reveal spatial wave patterns corresponding to the dominant NDs at each speed previously identified through spectral analysis. Subsequently, the amplitude distributions at time marker (A), where ND content alternation was observed in Fig. 12, are assessed. At $N70$, a distinct spatial wave pattern cannot be identified, although an ND3 pattern would have been expected. This might be due to the generally low vibration amplitudes at this time and the blades not yet oscillating at the M1 frequency. At $N85$, even though the amplitudes remain comparably low, a spatial wave pattern associated with ND2 becomes discernible, which is in line with the observations in Fig. 12. At $N97.5$, the spatial wave pattern characteristic of ND2 is already visible, especially when looking at blades no. 10 to 20, while the competing ND3 shows no discernible contribution.

Another notable observation can be made in the total deflection signal at time marker (A), where the overall amplitude exhibits a steep increase followed by a slower decay. However, the corresponding frequency content does not appear to be associated with M1. This observation is not assessed further in this study.

At this point, active modes and dominant NDs have been identified and confirmed by the formation of associated distinct spatial wave patterns seen in the time-domain BTTC deflection and SG strain signals. In order to ultimately judge on the presence and moment of flutter onset, the system damping needs to be estimated and assessed over time. As already apparent from the M1 bandpass-filtered signals in Fig. 13, the amplitude growth rates differ among the investigated flutter runs, making the estimation of the damping ratio based on experimental data of particular interest.

FIGURE 13: COMPARISON OF THE SINGLE-BLADE TEMPORAL EVOLUTION OF DEFLECTIONS APPROACHING FLUTTER COMPARING BTTC AND SG SIGNALS AND DERIVING NODAL DIAMETERS.

Based on the envelope of the M1 bandpass-filtered deflection signal of a selected blade, the temporal evolution of the total system damping is estimated according to the method described in section 2.2.4. The resulting damping trends for the three investigated flutter cases are presented in Fig. 14. Initially, the estimated damping values exhibit stochastic scattering, as no clear exponential growth can yet be fitted to the amplitude

FIGURE 14: COMPARISON OF THE SINGLE-BLADE TEMPORAL EVOLUTION OF DAMPING APPROACHING FLUTTER.

envelope. At a distinct point in time, however, the damping values begin to cluster in the negative regime, clearly indicating the onset of exponential amplitude growth and, consequently, the transition into self-excited flutter.

The approximate time of flutter onset can be inferred

from the moment when the dark-blue moving-mean trend line of the estimated damping ζ_{tot} crosses zero for the last time before remaining in the negative regime, as marked by (FO) in Fig. 14. For the cases at $N70$ and $N85$, this occurs at roughly revolution -500 . At $N70$, the amplitudes subsequently decrease temporarily around revolution -200 , causing the damping to rise briefly back into the positive regime before returning to negative, as indicated by the second dashed line. For $N97.5$, the flutter onset occurs earlier, around revolution -800 . It should be noted that this estimate serves only as an indicator for flutter onset, since the exact timing depends on the selected window size used for the moving-mean trend line calculation.

The evolution of the estimated system damping while in flutter differ between the different flutter cases at different speeds and dominant NDs. For $N70$ and $N97.5$, the damping continues to decrease slightly throughout the flutter event, though at different rates, indicating a progressive destabilisation of the aeroelastic system. In contrast, at $N85$, the damping remains nearly constant within the negative regime, apart from a short excursion towards positive values around revolution -100 . These variations in damping behaviour highlight the influence of operating condition, here at different speeds, and active ND on the strength and persistence of the aeroelastic instability.

To obtain a representative damping value for each individual blade, the amplitude- and R^2 -based gating procedure described in section 2.2.4 is applied to the full estimated damping signals. This filtering step rejects apparent fluctuations prior to flutter onset, ensuring that only damping values exhibiting a clear exponential amplitude progression are considered. The resulting blade-individual damping values for the three investigated flutter cases are shown in the upper part of Fig. 15. It appears that the blade-to-blade variation in the damping, thus the non-uniformity of aerodynamic work input to the blades, decreases for cases with a globally lower damping level. The damping varies in the range of 0.005% for M1 ND2 at $N97.5$, whereas the range is 0.015% for M1 ND3 at $N85$.

By averaging over all blades, a global total system damping is obtained for each flutter case. This approach is applied to all conducted flutter runs, and the resulting trends are presented in the lower part of Fig. 15. A distinction must be made between stepwise and continuous throttle manoeuvres. In the stepwise tests, manual incremental throttling leads to smaller amplitude growth rates and consequently to less negative damping, as well as lower maximum vibration amplitudes. In contrast, all continuous flutter runs are performed with a constant throttle-closing rate, resulting in generally stronger amplitude growth and higher negative damping. Overall, the results suggest a trend of increasing negative damping with rising operating speed, indicating a progressively more unstable aeroelastic system. The damping reduction at higher speeds is particularly steep for the continuously executed flutter onsets.

FIGURE 15: COMPARISON OF BLADE INDIVIDUAL DAMPING AND DERIVATION OF GLOBAL DAMPING FOR VARIOUS CONTINUOUS AND STEPWISE FLUTTER RUNS.

4 CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK

The presented experimental study aimed at an in-depth investigation of the aeromechanical stability behaviour of a modern transonic fan blisk under varying speed and loading conditions. The work focused on the identification and structural characterisation of fan blade flutter based on comprehensive measurements acquired at the new Fan Rig Darmstadt.

Within the explored operating envelope, detailed quasi-steady and transient mapping revealed a clear definition of the fan’s stable and unstable regimes. First flap flutter was identified as the stability limiting phenomenon across the whole examined speed range. Along the stability limit, four major nodal diameter transitions were observed with the dominant nodal diameters

being ND1, ND2, and ND3.

A modal and nodal decomposition of the measured blade tip deflection was performed based on capacitive blade tip timing data. The time-resolved results clearly demonstrated the formation of coherent inter-blade-phase-angles corresponding to the dominant NDs identified through spectral analyses. Comparisons with strain gauge and wall pressure transducer data verified the consistency of the BTTC-based modal and nodal identification. The analysis of the temporal evolution of ND content during throttling revealed alternating dominance between competing nodal diameters before one ultimately governs the aeroelastic instability. Furthermore, the system damping is estimated experimentally, confirming the presence of negative system damping while approaching the stability limit.

In accordance with the definition given by [19] and [20], the observed phenomenon satisfies the criteria of flutter, namely a self-excited oscillatory vibration very close to a blade’s natural frequency driven by aerodynamic energy input into the structure, thus negative damping, causing exponentially rising amplitudes. The derived negative damping ratios, together with the exponential amplitude growth, both determined by BTTC data, as well as the distinct M1 natural frequency identified in BTTC and SG spectra, provide conclusive evidence that the instability observed in the experiments constitutes flutter, or more precisely stall flutter. Differences in damping behaviour across the investigated speed lines further highlight the influence of operating condition and active ND on the strength and evolution of the instability.

In summary, the conducted measurement campaign at the Fan Rig Darmstadt demonstrated the capability of the new facility and its advanced instrumentation to depict and characterise aeroelastic phenomena such as flutter. The detailed characterisation of the structural modal, nodal, and damping behaviour provides a comprehensive experimental reference for the validation of numerical aeroelastic prediction tools as well as upcoming back-to-back comparisons with blade design variants. Furthermore, the work presented and the possibilities that arise with the rig capabilities can contribute to an enhanced understanding of fan flutter mechanisms and thereby support the development of more reliable design rules for future aero engines.

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